

Integration of Mobile Technologies to Support Remote Learning at the Basic Education Level in Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

The educational environment in Northern Nigeria faces significant challenges hindering teaching and learning progress, particularly in basic education, where security threats like banditry and kidnapping have complicated traditional educational methods, leading to disruptions and school closures. The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic further exacerbated these challenges, necessitating alternative instructional approaches. However, persistent security issues exacerbate difficulties faced by educators and learners, resulting in a decline in educational quality and continuity, while jeopardizing physical safety and hindering equitable access to education. Mobile technologies present a promising solution to address these challenges, especially in the Northwest region where banditry and kidnapping are prevalent. This research explores the dynamics of utilizing mobile technologies to support remote learning initiatives in basic education within Northwest Nigeria. Mobile learning, characterized by its accessibility, interactivity, and adaptability, holds immense potential to transform traditional educational practices, making learning more accessible, engaging, and personalized. By leveraging mobile technologies, educators can provide flexible and accessible educational solutions, ensuring continuity of learning despite security challenges. The TPACK model serves as a valuable framework for effectively integrating mobile technologies into remote learning environments, emphasizing the harmonious balance of technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge. Embracing mobile learning not only enhances educational accessibility but also empowers students to pursue self-directed learning, fostering a culture of lifelong learning.

Keyword: Mobile technologies, Remote Learning, Basic Education, Northern Nigeria, Security threats, TPACK model

Introduction

The educational environment in Northern Nigeria faces numerous obstacles that impede the progress of teaching and learning, particularly in the realm of basic education (Verspoor & Adriaan, 2008). The confluence of pervasive issues like banditry and kidnapping has resulted in an intricate situation, significantly impeding traditional educational methods (Sylvanus & Bernard, 2023). The region has grappled with disruptions attributable to security challenges, leading to the abduction of both students and teachers.

The closure of schools in response to the COVID-19 pandemic prompted educational institutions to seek alternative instructional approaches (Adedoyin & Soyinka, 2023). Nevertheless, the existing security situation in the region, characterized by ongoing banditry and targeted kidnappings, compounds the difficulties faced by educators and learners (Abubakar et al., 2021). The prevailing apprehension of potential attacks has disrupted the learning environment, causing a decline in the quality and continuity of education. These occurrences have not only jeopardized the physical safety of students and teachers but have also fostered an atmosphere of fear and uncertainty, hampering equitable access to education (Amy & Klinger, 2018).

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The field of education is undergoing a substantial transformation propelled by technological advancements, and mobile technologies are playing a crucial role in reforming teaching and learning approaches (Crompton, 2013). In the northwest zone of Nigeria, where challenges like banditry and kidnapping are widespread, the adoption of remote learning has become essential. This research endeavors to unravel the nuanced dynamics of employing mobile technologies to support remote learning initiatives, focusing on the unique context of basic education in Northwest Nigeria (Haruna, 2017).

The ubiquitous presence of mobile technologies in contemporary society is undeniable. Smartphones and tablets have become integral components of our daily lives, offering unprecedented access to information, communication, and interactive content (Reid et al., 2018). In the educational arena, the potential of these devices to transcend temporal and spatial constraints is particularly compelling. The advent of remote learning, accelerated by global events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has accentuated the need for flexible and accessible educational solutions (Cone et al., 2022). Kanno and Onyeachu (2015) characterize basic education as the fundamental level of education, which can also be construed as the most essential form of education provided to individuals. It serves as the cornerstone of education upon which all other educational progress relies. In this context, basic education can be likened to the foundation of a building, upon which all other structural elements and educational achievements are built.

Northwest Nigeria refers to the geographical region located in the northern part of Nigeria, which is a country in West Africa. It is one of the six geopolitical zones in Nigeria, and it encompasses several states, including but not limited to Kano, Katsina, Sokoto, Kaduna, Jigawa, Kebbi, and Zamfara. Northwest Nigeria is known for its diverse culture, historical significance, and economic activities such as agriculture, trade, and industry. It is an area with both urban centers and rural communities, and it plays a significant role in the socio-economic and political landscape of Nigeria. This region has faced various challenges, including security issues like banditry and kidnapping, which have had an impact on its educational and social development.

In many separate incidents across four states, students and their educators have been forcibly taken. In these occurrences, heavily armed individuals forcibly entered public boarding schools, firing their weapons indiscriminately, and forcibly moved the students into dense forests (Ojo et al., 2023). The victims were subjected to deplorable living conditions and eventually released after days or even weeks once a ransom was paid. In February, armed men also abducted nearly 300 girls from a boarding school located in Jangebe, Zamfara state (Osimen et al., 2018). Fortunately, the majority of these girls were later liberated.

The global aspiration to decrease illiteracy, address lack of knowledge, and promote educational accessibility, especially at the grassroots level, led to the initiation of the Education for All (EFA) framework, as outlined in the Jomtien Declaration (Easton & Malam, 2019). This treaty was introduced and ratified during the conference held in Jomtien, Thailand, in March 1990 (Egbe & Eze, 2009). As outlined by Dada (2004), access to education entails the chance and entitlement to partake in formal learning. It also encompasses the provision of equal opportunities to individuals who meet the criteria for receiving universal primary education, without regard to their socio-economic status, religious affiliation, gender, and other factors (Dreze & Sen, 2003).

Concept and definition of Mobile Learning at the Basic Education level

Mobile learning, often abbreviated as m-learning, refers to the use of mobile devices such as smartphones, tablets, or other portable electronic devices to facilitate learning and education (nail & Ammar, 2017). At the basic education level, which typically encompasses primary and secondary education, mobile learning can play a crucial role in enhancing the educational experience by leveraging the ubiquity and versatility of mobile technology (Dias et al., 2008). Accessibility of Mobile learning enables students to access educational content anytime, anywhere, as long as they have a compatible device and an internet connection (Motiwalla, 2007). This flexibility eliminates barriers to learning that may arise due to physical location or time constraints. Mobile devices offer interactive features such as touchscreens, multimedia capabilities, and educational apps that can make learning more engaging and enjoyable for students (Artal-Sevil, 2015). Interactive quizzes, educational games, and multimedia resources can enhance student motivation and participation (Zainuddin et al., 2020).

Mobile learning can be tailored to individual student needs and preferences. Educational apps and platforms often offer adaptive learning functionalities that adjust the pace and content of instruction based on each student's learning progress and performance (Zhu et al., 2016). Mobile devices facilitate collaboration and communication among students and teachers. Through messaging apps, discussion forums, and collaborative tools, students can interact with their peers and teachers, share ideas, collaborate on projects, and receive feedback in real-time (Sun et al., 2018; Dahal, 2022). Resource Accessibility of Mobile devices provide access to a vast array of educational resources, including e-books, videos, simulations, and online courses. This wealth of resources allows students to explore diverse topics, conduct research, and deepen their understanding of concepts beyond the confines of traditional classroom materials. Mobile learning fosters a culture of lifelong learning by enabling students to

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continue their education beyond the classroom (Criollo-C et al., 2021). With mobile devices, students can pursue self-directed learning, explore their interests, and acquire new skills even outside formal educational settings.

Mobile learning can accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences. Students can choose from a variety of learning materials and formats that best suit their individual needs, whether they prefer reading text, watching videos, listening to audio lectures, or engaging in interactive activities (Premlatha & Geetha, 2015). Mobile learning at the basic education level offers immense potential to transform traditional educational practices by making learning more accessible, engaging, personalized, and collaborative (Mehdipour, et al., 2013). However, it's essential to address challenges such as device accessibility, digital literacy, and equitable access to resources to ensure that all students can benefit from mobile learning opportunities.

Kadirire (2009) presents m-learning as a variant of e-learning that offers the flexibility of occurring at any time and in any place, facilitated by the use of mobile communication tools like mobile phones, personal digital assistants (PDAs), iPods, or similar compact and portable devices. However, contemporary viewpoints on mobile learning embrace m-learning as a transformative shift. In contrast, Keegan (2005) advocates for defining m-learning in a way that confines it to learning experiences facilitated exclusively through small, easily portable devices. He underscores the idea that these mobile devices can be carried with ease, fitting into a lady's handbag or a gentleman's pocket. Consequently, this definition aligns with a technocentric perspective, emphasizing the significance of mobile device size in defining m-learning. Furthermore, mobile learning entails establishing connections with institutional systems, including virtual learning environments (VLEs) and management information systems (MIS) (Hashemi et al., 2011).

According to Training Industry (2021) remote learning can be described as a mode of education in which the learner and the instructor, or the source of information, are geographically separated, making it impossible for them to convene in a traditional classroom environment. Typically, information is conveyed through technological means such as email, discussion boards, video conferences, or audio bridges, eliminating the need for any physical presence in a classroom setting; otherwise, it would fall under the categories of Hybrid or Blended Learning. Remote learning can take place either in real-time (synchronously) or at different times (asynchronously). It is also commonly referred to as Distance Education, Virtual Instruction, or Remote Training.

Theoretical Review

The TPACK model, introduced by Mishra and Koehler (2006), offers a valuable framework for effectively integrating mobile technologies into remote learning environments for basic education in Northwest Nigeria. TPACK underscores the intricate interplay among technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, and content knowledge, stressing the importance of achieving a harmonious balance among these elements to enhance the teaching and learning process. In the context of Northwest Nigeria, where educational access is hindered by factors such as banditry, kidnapping, and other criminal activities, the TPACK model remains essential for adapting mobile technologies to facilitate remote learning.

Application of TPACK Mobile Technologies for Remote Learning at Basic Education Level:

1. **Technological Knowledge (TK):** Educators in Northwest Nigeria must acquire proficiency in utilizing mobile technologies, including smartphones and tablets, for remote learning. This proficiency is crucial to ensure accessibility and the uninterrupted continuity of basic education in areas affected by security challenges.
2. **Pedagogical Knowledge (PK):** To effectively apply the TPACK model, teachers should employ pedagogical strategies that align with the capabilities of mobile devices, thus ensuring that remote lessons are engaging and interactive. Pedagogical knowledge is vital for educators in Northwest Nigeria as it enables them to design interactive lessons that make the most of the capabilities and applications of mobile technologies.
3. **Content Knowledge (CK):** TPACK encourages educators to tailor the curriculum to the local context and culture of Northwest Nigeria, thereby making the educational content more relevant and meaningful to students. Aligning content knowledge with the local context and culture is essential for enhancing the effectiveness of remote learning in Northwest Nigeria.

The Implications of Mobile Learning at the Basic Education level in Northwest Basic Education are drawn from the above concept and definition of Mobile Learning

1. Kadirire's definition of m-learning as a form of e-learning that can take place anytime and anywhere with the help of mobile communication devices is highly relevant to Northwest Nigeria (Kadirire, 2009). Given the security challenges and the dispersed nature of communities in the region, mobile technologies enable remote learning that is not bound by time or place. Students can access educational resources on their mobile devices, allowing for flexibility in their learning schedules and locations.

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2. Keegan's perspective on m-learning as a paradigm shift in education aligns with the region's needs and challenges (Keegan, 2005). In Northwest Nigeria, where traditional education may be disrupted by insecurity, m-learning represents a transformative approach. It allows basic education to continue despite security concerns, offering a lifeline for students who might otherwise be deprived of access to education due to kidnapping and banditry.

3. Keegan's perspective, which emphasizes the size and portability of mobile devices, becomes particularly significant in light of the security situation (Keegan, 2005). The small and easily portable nature of mobile phones is advantageous for students in Northwest Nigeria, as they can carry their learning devices discreetly and safely. This minimizes the risk of drawing attention to areas affected by security challenges.

Incorporating mobile technologies for remote learning in Northwest Nigeria offers a practical solution to address the obstacles posed by insecurity, such as kidnapping and banditry, to basic education. Mobile learning provides students with the means to access educational content from secure locations, reducing the need for physical movement to attend traditional schools. This not only ensures their safety but also empowers them with the opportunity to continue their education, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and accessible basic education system in the face of adversity.

Conclusion

The adoption of mobile learning in basic education in Northwest Nigeria offers a practical solution to mitigate the obstacles posed by insecurity, such as banditry and kidnapping. Mobile technologies enable remote learning, transcending temporal and spatial constraints, and ensuring educational continuity in the face of adversity. Embracing the TPACK model facilitates the effective integration of mobile technologies into educational practices, enhancing accessibility, engagement, and personalized learning experiences. Mobile learning empowers students to access educational resources securely, contributing to a more resilient and equitable basic education system.

Recommendations

Investment in Mobile Infrastructure: Governments and educational institutions ought to allocate resources towards enhancing mobile infrastructure, encompassing initiatives such as improving internet connectivity and implementing programs for distributing devices. These measures are essential for promoting fair and inclusive access to mobile learning resources across Northwest Nigeria.

Teacher Training: Educators should undergo training to effectively utilize mobile technologies for remote teaching, integrating teaching methodologies that are compatible with the functionalities of mobile devices.

Curriculum Adaptation: The curriculum needs to be adjusted to suit the local context and cultural nuances of Northwest Nigeria, thereby ensuring that educational content is pertinent and significant to students.

Collaborative Partnerships: Regular monitoring and evaluation of mobile learning initiatives are essential to assess their effectiveness and identify areas for improvement, ensuring sustained progress in enhancing basic education in the region.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Consistent monitoring and evaluation of mobile learning initiatives are crucial for evaluating their efficacy and pinpointing areas that require enhancement, thereby guaranteeing continual advancement in bolstering basic education in the area.

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